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THE STRATEGIC MOVES OF SUCCEEDING COMPANIES IN BULGARIA MIDST THE WORLD FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC CRISIS

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СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИТЕ ХОДОВЕ НА УСПЯВАЩИТЕ КОМПАНИИ В БЪЛГАРИЯ ПО ВРЕМЕ НА СВЕТОВНАТА ФИНАНСОВА И ИКОНОМИЧЕСКА КРИЗА

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Резюме: В настоящата статия се проучват стратегическите ходове на преуспяващите индустриални организации, официално огласили някои аспекти от своите постижения в бизнеса с местната общност чрез участието си в годишните изследвания на водещите икономически издания в България. Тук проличава, че успехите в бизнеса са възможни, дори и в отраслите - най-дълбоко засегнати от Световната финансова и икономическа криза.

Ключови думи: фирмена стратегия, индустриални организации, управление на кризи, стратегически мениджмънт;

Abstract. The current article is aimed at surveying the strategic moves of high-performing local industrial organizations that officially shared some aspects of their business achievements with local communities, participating in the surveys of leading periodicals in Bulgaria. It reveals that business success is possible even in the economic industries most affected by the World financial and economic crisis.

Keywords: company strategy, business strategy, industrial organizations, crisis management, strategic management.

JEL classification: L100, L190, L200, L210.

1. Introduction (survey actuality)

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The world financial and economic crisis affected Bulgaria by means of decreased orders for the local export-oriented companies and tightened lending conditions by the subsidiaries of foreign banks that represent the majority of financial institutions, operating on the local market. All this led to widespread business profit shrinkage and a bit later on to higher unemployment rates. In fact the economic perspective of the crisis prevails because Bulgaria functions within the terms of enacted currency board, although two potential dangers have threatened the financial stability of the national economy for three years, i.e.:

- The sluggish reactions in the spending manner of the public sector due to regular governmental change, slow pace of needed reforms, etc. and
- The financial situation in Greece, that controls above 30% of the local banking sector.

It may not be said that all the companies from most of the economic branches suffered to the same extent. For example the entities in the Pharmaceutical industry, the Energy sector and to some degree the so-called Public utilities came to be spared by the crisis and it was quite easy for their managers to continue the successful development of their organizations. At the same time economical branches as construction, transport, metallurgy, machine-building and others were deeply affected by the crisis, shrinking to great extent the annual production volumes in comparison to the boom years before 2008 (see figure 1).

Figure 1. The impact of world financial and economic crisis on different industries.

Source: [Capital, 2010]

So, it is not surprising that a sequel of laments by leading businessmen, politicians, public opinion figures, scientists and higher public officials followed as an array. "The obituary" of local business was created in advance to the forthcoming and aggravating business environment conditions. It is true that the current event of difficulty is the first

capitalist global crisis that has rushed on our economy since the 1930s. For sure, it may be true that the socialist period of development in the national economy has led to deeper changes in societal values, as well as the transition period that followed. So it is not surprising that the current situation looks a bit more bewildering and upsetting than it is in reality, because the majority of local managers lack a functioning pattern of shared basic assumptions, learned by them in the process of repeatedly successful solving the problems in the industrial organizations, concerned with external adaptation and internal integration (Schein, 2004). There are almost no valid scenarios of appropriate management initiatives, created by current generations of managers or taught to them by the earlier generations of business leaders as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems, arising in the crisis.

Figure 2. The bounces of industrial companies in Bulgaria in the continuum of local crises during the last two decades. *Source:* [Dimitrov, 2011]

On the other hand it may not be considered that business leaders of local industrial companies do not have enough experience with passing through local crises in the transition period (see figure 2). But the observed behaviors of “wait and see” – deliberate abstaining from interventions or asking for direct help from the state – forbidden by the EU legislation, in the crisis among a number of managers just reveals that the learning chances from the last two decades have not been utilized to full extent, i.e. the experienced difficulties in business were not accepted and used as key marker events for changing the set of basic assumptions, ruling dominating cultures in many local entities, leading to formulation of a (new) company vision, mission or credo to be implemented by

adequate change programs in the everyday management decisions and business activities of the personnel (Schein, 2009). It seems that most of the managers in local industrial organizations unconsciously rely on evolutionary culture change mechanisms. Considering the fact that only a small number of local organizations have passed through the longest possible life period of maximum 21 years as private entities, it sounds logical that managers' choices of culture change mechanisms is limited to those appropriate for companies in their founding and early growth stage. The potential of deeper cultural changes, associated with the midlife, maturity and decline stages of organizational life, remains inaccessible for the majority of industrial organizations or underutilized in the minority of them with longest existence because of demonstrated risk-averse management behavior, conflict of interests or total incompetence.

That is why it comes of great importance to study the "strategic moves" in the current crisis, undertaken by the minority of industrial organizations that succeeded in adapting to the changing business environment conditions in due course, thus increasing their profit levels or becoming leaders in minimizing.

2. Appropriate theoretical frames of potential strategic moves

The scientific interest is directed to company's overall development strategy, accepted as a bundle of chosen strategic characteristics (Campbell, Stonehouse, Houston, 2002). In this way some specific facets of chosen business strategy by each surveyed industrial organization may be identified and analyzed. But "the skeleton" company's overall development strategy is supposed to be shaped by managers' bodies, implementing aspects of different theoretical classifications of strategy. "The place", where a strategy is actually carried out in the companies, becomes an interesting issue, considering the options of:

- Network level, created by following of different collaborative strategies by the entities;
- Corporate level which comes to existence in the headquarters of big and diversified organizations and influences the other two levels;
- Business level that is projected and implemented in the strategic business units of a corporation (a holding company or consortium according to Bulgarian law), provided the "span of freedom", granted by the headquarters of the company. Of course there may be collision between corporate and business levels, if the company is small or medium-sized and operates in one business, but it is not the case if a difference between corporate and business level of strategy is made by means of sources of superior profitability (see figure 3);
- Although functional level is not of prime interest, in fact some aspects of it may come to surface as characteristics of the overall strategy of the entity.

Figure 3. The difference between corporate & business level of strategy by means of sources of superior profitability.

The preferred positioning of industrial companies on the continuum of corporate grand strategies secures important information about managers’ strategic choices (Campbell, Goold, Alexander, 1994):

- concentration strategy, vertical integration strategy and diversification strategy are the options within the group of growth strategies;
- following stability strategies comes as a second main alternative for the entities;
- the third path falls in the group of retrenchment strategies, i.e. turnaround strategy, divestment, bankruptcy and liquidation strategy.

The main types of diversification strategies, used in the surveyed entities, may substantially enrich “the strategic canvass” of success in crisis (see figure 4). Of course, considering the sensitiveness of “strategic matters” for management boards, additional information about diversification points of view, professed in the entities is unlikely to be found. That is why the different approaches to diversification are not of prime interest, i.e. portfolio approach, defining diversification as a desertion, the relation “diversification and system approach” and conglomerate growth (Paunov, 1995).

Figure 4. Types of diversification strategies.

Porter’s generic strategy framework provides the organization with three main strategic moves: differentiation, cost leadership and focus. But they are not accepted only as alternatives to include the ideas hybrid strategy framework in the analysis (Porter, 1980).

The product/market growth strategic framework may reveal business entities’ decisions, concerning produced products, related services and target markets (Ansoff, 1987). Since the survey encompasses succeeding companies in the current crisis, their attempts to grow are a leading priority, depending on whether an entity markets successfully new or existing products in new or existing markets. The original version of this matrix provides the managers with the following options: market penetration, market development, product development and diversification, each of which possesses specific characteristics. On the other hand the revisited and expanded version of Ansoff’s matrix provides the decision makers in the industrial companies with five strategic options, i.e. maintenance of the current competitive position, improvement of the current competitive position, harvesting and exiting from the market (business) (Campbell, Stonehouse, Houston, 2002). It has to be noted that good performance of entities on markets is always related to the implemented by them innovation strategies, although Bulgarian economy is categorized as “the innovation gap” within the EU (Drucker, 1984; ARC Fund, 2008-2010).

On the other hand globalization of local business is a phenomenon that has not happened during the transition period. That is why the five strategic postures, defined by Porter are unlikely to be a part of “the armor”, equipped by local industrial companies, i.e. global cost leadership, global differentiation, global segmentation and national responsiveness are not affordable for their managers (Grundy, 2004). Additionally, protected markets strategy is not allowed by the enacted EU legislation. The other side of the same coin - the internationalization of local industrial organizations, proceeds with pretty slow rates, but there are “leading stars” that make sense of studying the used entry mode alternatives, i.e. direct exporting, overseas production or assembly, international alliances and joint ventures, international mergers and acquisitions, international franchising and licensing (see figure 5) (Campbell, Stonehouse, Houston, 2002).

Figure 5. Key characteristics entry mode alternatives.

The reactions of local managers to the current crisis effects can be appraised by the lens of a traditional classification of business strategies for crisis times, illustrating a set of possible moves for local industrial companies, as follows (Paunov, 1995):

- Terminating the business, personnel layoffs, sales of all the assets, including the required legal steps to strike off the company from trade register.
- Reformulating the current business strategy.
- Implementing a strategy for an increase in revenues.
- Implementing a strategy for a decrease in costs.
- Implementing a strategy for a decrease or relocation of firm's assets.
- Creative search for any indirect form of subsidies from the state, because giving “*direct help*” to business entities is forbidden by EU regulations.

It is logical to be assumed that most of the local industrial companies pursue simultaneously more than one of the presented options in these turbulent times, according to the extent to which the crisis affected their industry and particularly their entity and the established competition levels and approaches among business rivals (Kotler, Caslione, 2009). Other classifications of business strategies may be added too, i.e. blue ocean concept, military source, chess and poker, but it is considered that their application either not widespread or not mentioned because of “firm security” issues (Wilson, Gilligan, 2009).

3. Survey methodology

The investigative approach to current crisis analysis concentrates on surveying the undertaken strategic moves of the so called “*succeeding industrial companies*” during the last 2-3 years, without setting any limitations on the industry (or industries) they operate in. Here, “*success rating*” is based on two different provisos, depending on the dominating situation in a definite industry, as follows:

- A succeeding company is one that has an increase in its profits for the last 3-4 years (from 2008 up to now);
- A succeeding company is one that has undergone the least decrease in sales (or profits) in comparison to its competitors;

The primary information in this research is acquired by careful selection and analysis of official publications, representing results from annual business surveys, accomplished by the analytical units and/or partners of leading economical periodicals in Bulgaria, i.e. newspaper “Capital” and newspaper “Bonnier Pari”. The first economic media concentrates its interest on the biggest companies. The second one defines profit margins as a priority which allows not only the biggest industrial organizations to be included in the “high-performing group in the crisis”, but also medium-sized and even small ones. In fact the information of used business strategies with some details of their characteristics represents:

- Direct citations of “spoken words”, i.e. business strategy labels, either by directors of these companies during interviews with economic journalists, or by the analyzers themselves;
- Relying on “strategy theory”, the researcher made logic conclusions of implemented business strategies in the companies, constructing summaries of proclaimed specific stories of organizations’ successes, structured as different sets of successive events, described by citations of managers’ words or economic journalists’ analyses. Finally a list of the followed overall business strategy in different industrial organizations was created, revealing in some cases even specific strategic attributes.

Reliability of information is guaranteed to a great extent by widespread Bulgarian people’s cultural trait to talk big, while professing the achieved excellent results of their companies and retell “*the story*” (in some cases maybe with features of saga or legend) in public on the pages of specialized economic media. Thus, a list of 47 “*succeeding organizations*” was created. On the other hand the researcher recognizes the acting assumption that people in general blow their own trumpets only when they achieve success and hide the dark sides of their failures. So it is normal to assume the existence of respondents’ unwillingness to share “*sensitive*” company information during interviews. That is why some survey limitations were defined, as follows:

- The components of company model for coping with crises can not be studied directly by reading and analyzing firm documents. That is why circumstantial conclusions about these components may be made by means of surveying the professed strategic postures or undertaken anti-crisis measures and executives’ attitude, associated with the current business situation.
- Detailed information of implemented company strategy is not accessible in the majority of the industrial organizations. That is why researcher’s interest is directed only to strategical aspects, shared by executives in public.
- The “*strategy*” research was directed only to succeeding companies whose managers were not afraid of sharing their stories with the local community in search of respect and admiration - a necessary corporate social responsibility initiative.

4. Survey results

The survey includes 47 companies – 22 from the annual business research, accomplished by the team of newspaper “Capital” and 25 firms from the annual business research, presented in the enclosures of “Bonnier Pari”. Surveying of the succeeding companies in the crisis generates important knowledge of the portfolio of strategic moves that brought “*success*” in these leading industrial companies, nevertheless the turbulence in the environment (see table 1).

On this base certain nuances may be outlined. **First**, the current crisis is defined and wisely used as a favorable period for design and implementation of production related investments by the majority of executive boards in leading industrial organizations.

Table 1. Attributes of implemented business strategies by profiting industrial companies.

\$x_1\$ MRF Frequencies		Responses		Percent of Cases
a Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.		N	Percent	
Strat_moves-freq(a)	Decrease in the number of personnel (dow	4	3.8%	8.5%
	Export	10	9.4%	21.3%
	Cost optimization /leadership	9	8.5%	19.1%
	Innovation strategy	13	12.3%	27.7%
	Production related investments	16	15.1%	34.0%
	Marketing related investments	4	3.8%	8.5%
	Site relocation	1	.9%	2.1%
	Related diversification	5	4.7%	10.6%
	Unrelated diversification	1	.9%	2.1%
	Fulfillment of ecological requirements	6	5.7%	12.8%
	Position defense	1	.9%	2.1%
	Organizational restructuring	1	.9%	2.1%
	Market development	2	1.9%	4.3%
	Employee training	5	4.7%	10.6%
	EU funding/ loans	7	6.6%	14.9%
	High quality standards	9	8.5%	19.1%
	Reasonable pricing	5	4.7%	10.6%
	Increase in productivity	2	1.9%	4.3%
	Sustainable development strategy	2	1.9%	4.3%
	Corporate social responsibility	1	.9%	2.1%
	Differentiation strategy	2	1.9%	4.3%
Total		106	100.0%	225.5%

Second, the innovation strategy proved to be the driver of effectiveness and efficiency improvements in leading industrial organizations, as well as the introducing of new products and/or services, but predominantly on existing markets. It may also be interpreted as a vivid manifestation of implemented differentiation strategy in comparison to firm's competitors.

Third, the export seems to be the preferred entry mode alternative, concerning presence on foreign markets by leading companies, because it requires the lowest levels of exercised control by the producer and minimum required resources in comparison to other moves such as licensing, joint venture and wholly owned subsidiary. It is obvious that executives in the succeeding companies are cautious in their initiatives and risk avert.

Fourth, cost optimization/ leadership is the next most powerful strategic move, implemented by leading companies, which comes of great importance for the long-term firm-level competitiveness, considering the comparatively lower value added of Bulgarian export in comparison to elder EU member states.

Fifth, keeping "High quality standards" became a priority for executives of leading industrial companies, since international acknowledged certification is a preliminary condition for establishing lasting advantageous relations with partners from developed countries.

Sixth, apparently the EU has its share of contribution to the sustainable development of the local economy, but the positive effect of Bulgaria's membership in it

has not reached its peak yet, because many industrial companies demonstrate low quality management and still find difficulties in embracing (preparing and managing projects) the EU institutions' offers in the forms of given cheap loans or free funding through the active programs, comprising the National frame of reference (2007 – 2013).

Seventh, the strategic move of fulfillment of ecological requirements comes to be an important tool for executive boards of leading organizations, too. But its wider application is associated with production decreases as a result of the crisis in some of "otherwise" succeeding companies, all of which belong to the group of privatized industrial enterprises that 20 years and more ago comprised the backbone of Bulgaria's economy. Now their managers have time and resources to modernize the production processes without necessarily rejecting clients' orders. On other hand these investments are not the first priority in managers' heads and their implementations have been delayed at least several times during the last decade, because they are not strongly related to the bottom line. In fact, the strict end terms of EU contemporary ecological requirements forced the managers to make expenses in this sphere, even during the crisis. Such requirements were included in the clauses of the privatization contracts during the period 1998 – 2001, but were not kept by the new owners, but the Post-privatization control agency did not take legal actions against them.

Eighth, minority of the leading companies officially declare "reasonable pricing", "employee training", "related diversification", "marketing related investments" and "decrease in number of personnel (downsizing) as attributes of their company strategies.

Ninth, there is negligible use of strategic moves as site relocation, unrelated diversification, organizational restructuring, and efforts, directed to achievement of increase in productivity, because all these are considered a bit more riskier.

Figure 6. Preferred strategic moves by the managers in the succeeding industrial companies.

Tenth, ideas of other perspectives to formulation and implementation (or explicit classifications) of corporate/ business strategies such as marshal arts or military strategy, and games of poker, chess or bridge, proved not to be preferred by the managers in the surveyed industrial organizations, since position defense is mentioned only once.

Eleventh, the officially proclaimed and desired strategic alternatives by the researchers and by the quasi-state institutions, such as sustainable development strategy, and corporate social responsibility are reported by a minority of leading enterprises. The widespread strategic choices among the managers of high-performing companies are shown on figure 6.

The available and retrieved data provided additional information about 31 of the total group of 47 leading industrial organizations, illustrating some related specific facets of the generally defined bundles of overall company's development strategy or 66%. The most interesting cases are presented below (see table 2).

Table 2. Related facets of bundles, comprising an overall company's development strategy

#	Industry	The bundle of overall company's development strategy	Related specific facets
1.	Foodstuff industry	(a) Marketing related investments; (b) Production related investments;	(a) Increased expenses in media advertising; (b) Working conditions improvements
2.	Foodstuff industry	(a) Site relocation; (b) Production related investments	Concentrating production activities in Bulgaria
4.	Chemical industry	(a) Production related investments; (b) Fulfillment of ecological requirements	(a) Investment in new production capacity; (b) Modernization of production might
5.	Glass industry	(a) Position defense; (b) Production related investments	(a) Maintenance of production volumes without radical changes and cataclysms; (b) Investment in new production might
6.	Chemical industry	(a) Cost optimization/ leadership; (b) Organizational restructuring; (c) Decrease in the number of personnel (downsizing)	(a) Stick to the core activities/ competences; (b) Discontinuing of unprofitable activities; (c) Production processes optimization; (d) Transport activity is transformed into a separate company
7.	Machine building	(a) Innovation strategy; (b) Market development; (c) Production related investments;	(a) Investments in production processes are associated with achievement of potential decrease in prime cost; (b) Increase in production capacity
8.	Construction	(a) High quality standards; (b) Reasonable pricing; (c) Export; (d) Employee training; (e) Production related investments; (f) Increase in productivity	(a) Doesn't work with subcontractors; (b) Shorter terms of project accomplishment; (c) Use of modern equipment; (d) Increase in production capacity
9.	Construction	(a) Cost optimization/ leadership; (b) Reasonable pricing; (c) Related diversification; (d) Employee training	(a) Lower profit margins; (b) Investment in human capital development;
10.	Construction	Cost optimization/ leadership	Decrease in expenses in the sphere of: employee remuneration, technical equipment, and building plots.
11.	Construction	EU funding/ loans	Participation in infrastructure projects, funded by EU
12.	Foodstuff industry	High quality standards	Collaboration in working out and implementation of new quality standards
13.	Furniture, sports equipment	(a) Reasonable pricing; (b) Innovation strategy	(a) Active search of clients; (b) Higher work dynamics; (c) Lower profit margins
14.	Construction	EU funding/ loans	Participation in infrastructure projects.
15.	Energy production	(a) High quality standards; (b) Sustainable development strategy; (c) Production related investments	(a) ISO certificates for quality, environment, and health and safety work conditions, change in management philosophy; (b) Change in policy of property expropriation in front of the mining activities; (c) Successful management characteristics: modern strategy, proactive policy, innovative thinking and hiring appropriate employees; (d) Timely payments to the partners; (e) Modernization of equipment
16.	Foodstuff industry	(a) Fulfillment of ecological requirements; (b) EU funding/ loans; (c) Cost optimization/ leadership, (d) Export, (e) High quality standards, (f) Innovation strategy	ISO 14000, energy efficiency projects,

#	Industry	The bundle of overall company's development strategy	Related specific facets
17.	High-tech	Innovation strategy	Free will and search of the necessary quantity of disorder in electro physics, to embrace doubts, while walking the winding road to clarity, and support of experiments.
18.	Non-ferrous metallurgy	(a) Innovation strategy, (b) EU funding/ loans, (c) Production related investments, (d) Fulfillment of ecological requirements	(a) Modernization of production processes, (b) Participation in infrastructure projects, (c) Increase in production capacity
19.	High-tech	(a) Employee training, (b) Innovation strategy, (c) Production related investments, (d) High quality standards	German order – Bulgarian enthusiasm
20.	Construction	(a) High quality standards, (b) Increase in productivity, (c) Reasonable pricing, (d) Cost optimization/ leadership	(a) First, infrastructure is built, then the houses are erected; (b) Shorter terms of project accomplishment
21.	Energy production	(a) Fulfillment of ecological requirements, (b) Sustainable development strategy	Maintenance of a health and work safety information management system
22.	Brewing	(a) Corporate social responsibility, (b) Differentiation strategy, (c) Innovation strategy, (d) Production related investments, (e) Marketing related investments	(a) Updating product portfolio, (b) Investments in development of company's trade marks
23.	Ferrous metallurgy	(a) Cost optimization/ leadership, (b) Production related investments	The debtors perform the construction activities at the site of the company.
24.	Wine	(a) Export, (b) High quality standards, (c) Reasonable pricing, (d) Differentiation strategy, (e) EU funding/ loans	Participation in EU projects
25.	Construction	(a) EU funding/ loans, (b) Employee training, (c) Production related investments	(a) New home shop – a new marketing approach, (b) Construction of business parks, (c) Participation in infrastructure projects, (d) Investment in equipment

The results show that the companies from “Bonnier Pari” survey have revealed more attributes of their strategic moves. The additional information from both surveys provides the opportunity of making thorough analysis and reaching some more conclusions. **First**, it may be inferred that the greater part of these companies that realized lower degrees of utilization of current production capacity in the short run because of the crisis-time impacts, have initiated projects for building new production sites or modernization and/or increase in the current production might of existing production facilities.

Second, the applied marketing instruments are limited to intensive advertisement, establishment of closer relations with target clients and vendors of related services and/or products. This situation may be accepted as a manifestation of low levels trust to modern marketing approaches by the managers in these companies.

Third, a small part of them initiated efforts in the sphere of employee training which costs may be shared by the company and EU funding, provided through different operative programs, such as “*Competitiveness*” and “*Human resources*”. Considering lower levels of client orders for some of the enterprises, this strategic move ensures the maintenance and development of business specific employee skills, abilities and knowledge.

Fourth, a minority of them chose to restructure their product portfolios, thus concentrating to producing products or delivering services through which higher value added is generated. This facet in the strategic moves by some of the leading industrial enterprises makes a stand against the traditional market orientation approach of the

majority of companies to try to sell what they can produce, and not to pay attention to customer preferences.

Sixth, unbundling of different functional spheres in the industrial organization as separate companies is an old approach that is preferred again by some managers to escape enacted law procedures during mass layoffs and spare labor costs, associated with this process.

Seventh, a minority of companies dare reinvent their business model, trying to re-/dis-solve in a better way the issues of their customers. Examples may be found in the construction industry where a minority of companies first build the infrastructure, and then buildings or create “*new home shop*” to deliver on the same site related services to its clients as property financing sources, furniture sellers, etc.

Eighth, the current crisis is accepted as a key marker event by the senior managers in a minority of leading companies and forced them to re-define their mission, vision and/or credo, thus initiating substantial organization culture changes in order to improve form’s external adaptation and internal integration.

Ninth, a minority of leading organizations try to cooperate with their partners in an innovative way. For example a company may not take legal actions against a debtor, but invite the other company to deliver certain necessary services.

Tenth, as a whole it may be concluded that managers of the succeeding companies share a long-term orientation to lower profit margins and tolerate higher levels of discipline, concerning contracted end-terms of implemented projects and due payments to partners.

Another interesting point is that companies in the survey used different numbers of strategic moves, mentioned by interviewed managers or concluded by the researcher as a part of basic bundle of overall company’s development strategy. It is detected that the majority of companies claim to use just one strategic move (42.6%) and the greater the number of detected strategic moves, the less the number of applying organizations (see table 3). Of course the overall business strategy has simpler content in small and medium-sized companies which has to be taken in account. On the other hand the sensitiveness of this theme prevents managers’ sharing further details in their strategic moves in the crisis.

Table 3. Number of strategic moves, undertaken by industrial organizations as a part of the basic bundle of company’s overall development strategy.

Number of strategic moves		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	one strategic move	20	42.6	42.6	42.6
	two strategic moves	11	23.4	23.4	66.0
	three strategic moves	6	12.8	12.8	78.7
	four strategic moves	6	12.8	12.8	91.5
	five strategic moves	2	4.3	4.3	95.7
	six strategic moves	2	4.3	4.3	100.0
	Total	47	100.0	100.0	

The number of the mentioned strategic moves in the periodicals is classified by the concrete survey it belongs to, which can be seen on figure 7. On this base it can be concluded that the “Bonnier Pari” survey gives more detailed information about chosen strategic postures by industrial organizations in comparison to “Capital” survey.

It comes as a surprise, but 27.7% of the surveyed organizations operate in the foodstuff industry, 19.1% function in the construction industry, and each of the following four industries comprises 8.5% of the total number of surveyed enterprises, i.e. machine building, chemical industry, high-tech industry and non-ferrous metallurgy. Table 4 presents a detailed view of the branches of industry the group of surveyed companies belong to.

Figure 7. Number of mentioned strategic moves as a part of basic bundle of company’s overall development strategy by different surveys.

Table 4. Branches of industry the surveyed industrial organizations operate in.

Branches of industry	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Pharmaceutical industry	2	4.3	4.3	4.3
Machine building	4	8.5	8.5	12.8
Foodstuff industry	13	27.7	27.7	40.4
Chemical industry	4	8.5	8.5	48.9
Glass industry	1	2.1	2.1	51.1
High-tech	4	8.5	8.5	59.6
Non-ferrous metallurgy	4	8.5	8.5	68.1
Construction	9	19.1	19.1	87.2
Furniture, sports equipment	1	2.1	2.1	89.4
Energy production	2	4.3	4.3	93.6
Ferrous metallurgy	3	6.4	6.4	100.0
Total	47	100.0	100.0	

But if surveyed companies are divided by periodicals' surveys, a richer picture reveals. Only "Bonnier Pari" survey encompasses entities from industries as ferrous metallurgy, energy production, furniture and sports equipment. On the other hand only "Capital" survey includes entities from industries as pharmaceutical industry, machine building and glass industry. High-performing organizations from economic branches of foodstuff industry, chemical industry, high-tech, non-ferrous metallurgy and construction are presented in both surveys, although with differences of the numbers of entities which can be best notices in the construction sphere.

Figure 8. The participants in the two surveys by branches of industry.

It is evident that there are not only similarities, but also certain nuances in the preferred strategic postures by the two groups of surveyed companies, formed by the economic periodicals' annual research (see figure 9). In both groups the companies prefer "production related investments", "export", "innovation strategy", "cost optimization /leadership", and "fulfillment of ecological requirements". The nuances can be traced in two directions:

- **First**, the group, presented by "Bonnier Pari" competes on markets with strategic moves as: "high quality standards", "EU funding /loans", "reasonable pricing", "increase in productivity", "sustainable development strategy", "differentiation strategy, etc. The group of companies, presented by "Capital" did not mention all these. On the other hand a small number of the members from the last group are the only ones that implement "market development", "organizational restructuring", "site relocation", "unrelated diversification", "decrease in the number of personnel (downsizing)", and "position defense".

- **Second**, "cost optimization /leadership", "innovation strategy", "fulfillment of ecological requirements", and "employee training" are preferred more among the "Bonnier

Pari” group. On the other hand “export”, “marketing related investments”, and “related diversification” are preferred more among the “Capital” group.

Figure 9. The preferred strategic moves and economic media survey the company belongs to

6. Conclusions

Nevertheless how companies define their successes and the dominating industry-specific conditions they operate in, it is evident that the World financial and economic crisis has not overwhelmed the will for organizational survival and development, deeply engrained in managers’ mindset in local organizations. Success proves to be possible even in the industries most affected by the crisis, because of brilliant management ideas that led to reinventing current business models, accepting needed change as opportunity for growth and development and carefully appraising the associated risks for the entities.

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